

Twitter-based Segregation Analysis: The Many Faces of Social Media Discourses

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Abstract

This study contributes to the empirical literature assessing what the extension through social media means for ideological segregation of public discourses. By performing a Twitter-based hyperlink-analysis, I measure segregation of two large, dynamic, and heterogeneous social media discourses that took place in 2015 in German-speaking countries. The analysis reveals that only in one case (the refugee discourse) segregation of social media surpassed segregation of traditional media, whereas in the second discourse (Greek debt discourse) segregation levels were even. This result aligns with recent literature stating that ideological segregation is only one among many possible consequences of social media engagement.

Introduction

The extension of public discourses through social media entitled common citizens and weakly organized groups to participate in full independence of traditional media organizations. The entitlement raised hopes to render tangible the deliberative ideal of a single public sphere in which all affected citizens bring up and reflect arguments from all available perspectives (Lincoln Dahlberg, 2001; Graham, 2012; Karlsson, 2012; Papacharissi, 2002). Yet, more skeptical researchers claim that social media discussions hardly pursue deliberative goals (Habermas, 2006, p. 423; C. Sunstein, 2009). Most prominently, they claim that social media forums are strongly segregated along ideological foundations and that they fail to facilitate the encountering and reflection of opposing views that is so important within the deliberative perspective (McPherson, Smith-Lovin, & Cook, 2001).

Ideological segregation could present a major challenge to democracy, due to its potential to radicalize opinions. Within segregated discussion forums, the imbalance of available information as well as the fear to argue against majority reinforce participant's initial opinions and hamper accommodation across ideological divides (D. C. Mutz, 2006; C. R. Sunstein, 2006). Rather than as deliberative forums, social media outlets might function as echo chambers in which moderate and nuanced opinions turn to radical ones (C. R. Sunstein, 2006, p. 55). These considerations demonstrate the importance of segregation analysis in order to learn how the end of journalists' monopoly affects democratic quality of public discourse.

A great deal of empirical literature finds one or the other supportive argument for Sunstein's prediction of ideological segregated social media and the rather harmful consequences on opinions, tolerance, and empathy (Adamic & Glance, 2005; Baum & Groeling, 2008; Conover, Ratkiewicz, & Francisco, 2011; D. Mutz, 2002). Nevertheless, the segregation debate remains unresolved as perennial scholars discover counter-evidences and point out blind-spots in previous research (O'Hara & Stevens, 2015). The present study addresses their concern that the scopes of most previous

studies is limited to single platforms such as Twitter (Conover et al., 2011), Facebook (Jacobson, Myung, & Johnson, 2015; Robertson, Vatrapu, & Medina, 2010) or the blogosphere (Adamic & Glance, 2005), whereas only few studies obtain a broader perspective (Brundidge, 2010; Gentzkow & Shapiro, 2011). Approaches allowing a comparison between multiple areas within a public discourse tend to end up with more optimistic findings. In particular, these studies find social media segregation to be at a similar level as in traditional media and less pronounced than in offline encounters (Brundidge, 2010; Gentzkow & Shapiro, 2011). Overall, this suggests that social media participants encounter at least a similar degree of opposing arguments than people who stay offline.

By upholding the need to measure social media segregation in relative terms—facilitating comparison between other areas of public discourses—the present study compares segregation between social media (online sites with public-authored content) with segregation of online outlets of traditional media (online sites with journalists-authored content). Hereby, the study incorporates numerous types of online media ranging from traditional media outlets, blogs to small, spontaneously emerged Facebook pages.

For estimating ideological segregation of online media, I analyze a large dataset of hyperlinks addressing a myriad of social and traditional media outlets. The hyperlinks stem from overall one million discourse-specific Twitter posts and form the starting point for a principal coordinate analysis that is capable to proxy ideological segregation of media. More accurately, the analysis outputs a principal coordinate on which the media spread by ideological tendentious twitter-users populate the poles (indicating a segregated readership) and the media whose spreaders are less clearly to assign to an ideological stance populate the center (indicate a less segregated readership). According Sunstein' arguments, it is then to expect that social media reveal a more polarized coordinate than traditional media.

For the study, I analyze and compare two public discourses, namely, the discourse of the *Greek debt negotiations* and the *European refugee crisis* in German-speaking countries. The two discourses feature similar characteristics and are thus highly usable for a comparative analysis. A common theme connects both topics as they both crystallize around solidarity with foreign people in need. In the year 2015, both discourses dominated the reporting in the press and news channels in summer (*Greece debt negotiations*) and autumn (*European refugee crisis*). Analyzing two cases not only promises to gain wider insights on social media usage, it also extends the range of available robustness tests.

The article consists of four chapters: the first chapter contains a review of theoretical and empirical literature about the segregation of social and traditional media and it outlines the empirical blind spots in previous literature. The second chapter introduces and validates the applied method. In the third and fourth chapters, I demonstrate the method by the two case studies. In the last chapter, I embed the findings within the theoretical discussion whether and to what extent social media are conducive for segregation of public discourse and its consequences on the normative assessment of public discourses.

The Segregation of Social Media Discourses: Empirical Blind Spots

The academic literature is engaged in a contentious debate about the democratic values of political social media discussions. On the one hand, digital enthusiasts emphasize social media' participatory, mobilizing as well as informative functions to revive public discourses, to accommodate across ideological camps, and even to strengthen minorities (L. Dahlberg, 2011; Stromer-Galley, 2002). On the other hand, digital sceptics stress that social media regularly prove to be a marketplace for radical and only weakly reflected opinions that promotes—more than other values—segregation and opinion radicalization (C. Sunstein, 2009).

Within the latter scenario, the psychological concept of homophily has an important role to play. Homophily is human's tendency to avoid conflict and assort themselves in group of likeminded (McPherson et al., 2001). As consequence of homophily, social-media participants tend to assort themselves in insular groups of likeminded (C. R. Sunstein, 2006). Empirical studies confirm that in many situations social-media networks excel by strong fragmentation with many links among homogenous entities and few links across ideological boundaries (Adamic & Glance, 2005; Hargittai, Gallo, & Kane, 2008; Lawrence, Sides, & Farrell, 2010).

An even larger threat of segmented discourses is the prospect of self-reinforcing mechanisms. Sunstein predicts that discussions within groups of likeminded drive participants' opinions "*toward a more extreme point in the direction indicated by the members' pre-deliberation tendencies*" (C. R. Sunstein, 2002, p. 176). What follows is that readers of segmented media outlets become even more radicalized, less tolerant for opposing views (D. C. Mutz, 2006). Among the factors that might stimulate such polarization process is the search for social approval, the fear of expressing alternative views, and a biased pool of arguments prevailing in homogenous groups (C. R. Sunstein, 2002).

However, it is not only homophily that might drive segregation. Pariser (2011) argues that on social-media platforms both recommendations and filtering software create a filter bubble that is "a unique universe of information for each of us." Within filter bubbles there is not much that challenge the reader's biases and knowledge (D. Mutz & Martin, 2001).

A further argument for segregation within the social-media sphere originates in its computer-mediated nature. Expressing opinions on social media does not bear the same level of perceived social risks than it would have in face-to-face environments (Stromer-Galley, 2002, p. 27). To the extent that is not observable in face-to-face conversations, participants of computer-mediated discussions treat each other with insults and humiliations. In short, the way people communicate with each other in

online forums discourages more nuanced and moderating voices. Hence, social media not only change the way people communicate, they also induce a significant participation bias that shapes social media more and more as soapboxes for political nonconformists (Ekdale, Namkoong, Fung, & Perlmutter, 2010, p. 15; McKenna, 2007; Wallsten, 2008). Based on these considerations, I hypothesize social media are conducive to segregation in public discourses.

While many previous studies confirmed this hypothesis, numerous blind spots and uncharted counter-evidences exist. In particular, some recent empirical literature raises doubts whether social media are so conducive for the formation of enclaves and whether enclave discussions are as harmful as predicted (see also O'Hara & Stevens, 2015). A major concern is that not many methods allow grasping social-media sphere in a comprehensive way. For example, many studies of the blogosphere tend to limit their sample on A-list blogs, whereas they neglect the grassroots level.¹ This approach is problematic as soon one recognizes that most prominent political bloggers are at least as professional as columnists in traditional media organizations in terms of education and professional backgrounds (Hindman, 2008). Hence, since A-list bloggers are only weakly comparable to average social-media users, the findings of such studies shed only some light on the general consequence of social-media usage. In the study at hand, the “social” in “social media” takes center stage and incorporates small, spontaneously generated public-authored outlets into the analysis.

The user-centered measurement of segregation is a further concern of many previous empirical studies. Frequently, the studies measure segregation by degree of homogeneity within a specific user network. Yet, empirical evidence suggests that users still seek and find opposing information, albeit social ties are strongly homogenous. For instance, Conover et al. (2011) show that the *retweet* network on Twitter (user level) is highly polarized, while the *mention* network (content level) is

¹ Many studies limit its scope on top-ranked blogs identified by A-list or BAI indices (Dave Karpf, 2005). Some rare exceptions use randomized samples (Herring et al., 2005; Wallsten, 2005) or all observed blogs (Adamic & Glance, 2005).

not. In fact, also with strong ties among friends, Internet users—more than non-users—encounter a variety of political arguments, including those that run counter to their own political views (Brundidge, 2010, p. 696; Gentzkow & Shapiro, 2011; Lev-On & Manin, 2009). This fits to Stromer-Galley's observation that social-media participants indicate a great curiosity to seek encounters with opposing perspectives (Stromer-Galley, 2002). Thus, similar to Lawrence et al (2010) and Gentzkow and Shapiro (2011), the present study refrains from analysis of author networks and rather focus on readership segregation.

Most importantly, the vast majority of previous research focuses on single platforms, either Twitter, Facebook, or the Blogosphere (Adamic & Glance, 2005; Akoglu, 2014; Gruzd & Roy, 2013; Hargittai et al., 2008; Himelboim, McCreery, & Smith, 2013; Lawrence et al., 2010; Robertson et al., 2010). There are two problems with such case studies. On the one hand, when polarization takes place in one or the other social network, there is no necessity that the social-media sphere is generally segregated. On the other hand, since no reference category is included—with the degree of segregation elsewhere in the public discourses is unknown—, these studies do not enable making statements about social media's particular role for segregation. Prominent studies that include such reference categories find the segregation of social (or digital) media to be moderate or non-existing (Gentzkow & Shapiro, 2011; Lin, Bagrow, & Lazer, 2011). Hence, in the present article, I gather data not only from user-driven media but also from online outlets of traditional media, what promises to understand better social media's effect on public discourses.

Gentzkow and Shapiro's (2011) work is at the forefront when it comes to grasp media segregation at a macro level. By a combination of various methods and data sources, the authors measure the ideological segregation of online and offline news outlets as well as segregation of face-to-face encounters. They find segregation values for both online and offline news consumption to be much lower than the segregation value of face-to-face encounters. Yet, the authors refrain from a distinction between

journalists- and public-authored media. Precisely this distinction is at the heart of the present study. It reflects a fundamental transformation triggered by the extension of public discourses through social media.

Hyperlink-based Segregation Measurement

In the following, I introduce the hyperlink-based technique to analyze segregation of online public discourses including both traditional and social media. The technique consists of the following steps: I use hyperlinks in Twitter data to identify media outlets participating in the public discourses under study and estimate the segregation of outlets by analyzing hyperlinking patterns.

I. Identification of Media Outlets

Users of the micro blogging service Twitter extensively spread links to newspaper articles, blog entries, pictures, videos, and Facebook entries located everywhere in the cyberspace. Some scholars claim that the extensive usage of hyperlinks shape Twitter as a broadcasting medium that can be compared with press agencies or news feeds (Cha, Benevenuto, Haddadi, & Gummadi, 2012; Hughes & Palen, 2009). Similar, other scholars consider Twitter as a “dissemination system” for any kind of content that is relevant to a public- or group-based discussions (Ediger et al., 2010).

Owing to its outstanding broadcasting function, I also use Twitter to identify media outlets of a public discourse. To identify outlets, I started collecting half a million tweets from a certain date that was contributing to one of the two discourses. For this purpose, I accessed Twitter’s full-text search engine and recorded tweets containing at least one of several keywords. The keywords described the discourses under study in the German-speaking countries in adequate precision.² The collection

² In case of the Greek debt discourse, the following query for full-text search were used: *griechenland OR staatsbankrott OR greece OR schuldenkrise OR grexit OR varoufakis OR tsipras OR syriza OR grisis OR grexcident OR greferendum OR oxi OR greekreferendum lang:de*. In case of the asylum discourse, the query “*flüchtling OR fluechtling OR flucht OR asyl OR aufnahmezentrum OR migration OR dunkeldeutschland OR pegida OR schauthin OR heidenau OR migrant OR refugee lang:de*” were used. I selected most of the keywords after a weeklong pre-test. Two weeks after the start, I complimented the list by a few newly emerged hashtags that proved to be popular. To collect the tweets, I used the social network-analyzing service *netlytic*

process took about two months per topic starting in mid-June for the Greek debt discourse and mid-August for discourse about the European refugee crisis. In an average day, I collected about 10,000 new tweets. About 71% of the million tweets contained at least one hyperlink. Yet, for this study, not all hyperlinks are of interest:

First, I am interested in hyperlinks that target social media outlets. I define social media as online resources with public-authored content (common citizens or grassroots communities).

Second, in order to understand whether segregation in social media is high or low, I additionally incorporate traditional media outlets as a reference category. I define traditional media outlets as online resources, which are authored by media agencies maintaining conventional distribution channels (i.e., cable, satellite, radio, and press). Hence, the relevant criterion deciding to which category an outlet belongs is the author and not the outlets' genre or type. Ambiguous cases—for instance semi-official websites of journalists—are assigned to the traditional media as soon as they refer to a traditional media organization in the *about* section, the *site-notice*, or the header of the website.

Third, I also monitor outlets from individuals or institutions having privileged access to the public discourse. Most of them are political parties, politicians, governments, parliaments, unions, churches, research institutes, and supra-national organizations. This category is particularly useful to validate the method as they provide important orientation marks within the ideological space. Here as well, revealed institutional affiliation in the *about* section, the *site-notice*, or the header of the website is a requirement.

I discarded many hyperlink targets from the analysis. First, to increase the confidence level in the estimated ideological positions, I discarded media spread by less than five Twitter users (see next chapter for detailed reasoning). Then, I excluded

(<http://www.netlytic.org>). It runs the search query every 15 minutes and returned at the time a maximum of 1,000 tweets per each run. Hence, in the very peak times, the service did not capture all available tweets.

hyperlinks in tweets that were commercials or false positives (i.e., hyperlinks address websites of companies or internet services with no substantial relation to the topics under discussion). About a quarter of the remaining targets were online-only news sites or “bridge blogs”, which I did not consider as social media nor as traditional media outlets (David Karpf, 2008, p. 374). Additionally, I removed hyperlinks that target utterances on collaborative platforms such as photo-, video-, music-, or file-sharing platforms or Wikipedia pages. Furthermore, a significant amount of the collected hyperlinks addresses content on the Twitter platform. Since I use Twitter only as a research instrument and not as a research object, I also removed these hyperlinks from the dataset.

Overall, I end up with identifying about 70,000 utterances (e.g., blog entries, articles, etc.) uttered on 1,577 media outlets (e.g., newspapers, bloggers, and Facebook pages).³ I categorized 869 online sites as social-media category, 429 as traditional media organizations, and the remaining 279 to the category of privileged actors. The social-media category predominately entails collective (i.e., group-authored) blogs. Other outlets were individual blogs, private homepages, or Facebook pages. Most of the traditional media outlets were official websites of local, regional, or national newspapers, as well as radio and television stations. Many other outlets were the online sites of employed journalists. The most dominant outlets within the category of privileged actors were the official websites of parties as well as private homepages or blogs of politicians.

II. How to Harvest Segregation Data from Hyperlinks

The Twitter network is one of the most studied social network. By analyzing who follows who, who retweets who, or who referenced who, researchers estimate many different spatial maps of the Twitter sphere (Barberá & Sood, 2015; Barberá, 2015; Conover et al., 2011; Golbeck, Park, & Hansen, 2011).

³ Appendix II features the full list of identified media outlets.

In contrast to the aforementioned studies, I do not analyze the Twitter network as such. Instead, I use the Twitter as an instrument to learn about what is happening in the other parts of the cyberspace (see An, Gummadi, Crowcroft, & Quercia, 2012 for a similar attempt). This is possible due to the strong political dimension of hyperlink patterns. Not only on Twitter but elsewhere in the cyberspace, the very act of linking, not linking, or removing a link can be viewed as acts of association, non-association, or disassociation (Adamic, 2008; Barnett, 2011, p. 79; Jacobs, Cook, & Delli Carpini, 2009; Rogers, 2010, p. 117). Research on Twitter confirms that Twitter users tend to link utterances to support their personal view on the state of the world (Thimm, Einspänner, & Dang-Anh, 2012, p. 301). The ideological essence of hyperlink patterns allows to estimate an ideological map containing on the edges the most segregated media outlets (the ones that are spread only by users from a certain ideological camp) and in the moderate fields the integrated ones (the ones that are spread by users from a broader ideological range).

In order to estimate such a map, I, first, model the ideological distance for any two media outlets (say A and B) by dividing the number of Twitter users that spread both outlets, $U_{(A \cap B)}$, by the number of users that spread the less popular outlet, $\min(U_A, U_B)$. The full distance formula reads as follows:

$$Distance_{AB} = 1 - U_{(A \cap B)} / \min(U_A, U_B)$$

The subtracter within the formula resembles to the Jaccard similarity coefficient, as it only differs by the denominator $\min(U_A, U_B)$. The reason for not using the original denominator ($U_A \cup U_B$) is the enormous popularity differences within my dataset. The modification facilitates that even small niche blogs spread by only five Twitter users may archive a close ideological position to large traditional media, such as the most popular online magazine *Spiegel Online*.

With above formula, I populate for n identified outlets a distance matrix with a scale of $n \times n$. The matrix serves, then, as a basis for principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) as a specific type of multidimensional scaling (Gower, 1966). PCoA is a

method to calculate distances between subjects in a multidimensional space. In order to correct the typically overestimated ideological distances between unpopular outlets, I apply PCoA with point weights (Gower & Krzanowski, 1999; Oksanen et al., 2015). Overestimation originates in the low likelihood that a Twitter user who spreads an unpopular online site also knows, reads, and spreads a second unpopular site, although ideological alignment might be given.⁴

III. Validation

I expect PCoA to make apparent the latent ideological structure caused by the ideological compliance between the Twitter users and the hyperlinked outlets. As I will demonstrate in the following, PCoA solved this task flawlessly and identified the segregation of the online outlets on the well-known ideological axis from left progressive to right conservative standpoints.

The PCoA identifies for each public discourse a principal coordinate that clearly stands out from the other coordinates but only explain about 6-7% of the total variance (Greek debt discourse: 5.7%, refugee discourse: 6.9%). This rather low value of explained variance is not surprising since ideological compliance might be the major—but by no means the only—predictor of hyperlinking activities. Many other non-political factors influence decisions of whether an article should be linked or not (e.g. shared sense of humor, geographical region, familiarity, randomness, etc.). Low goodness-of-fit values are not an essential menace for PCoA as well as for other multidimensional scaling configurations. In fact, low goodness of fit levels occur frequently, in particular in configurations with high number of considered dimensions (Borg, Groenen, & Mair, 2013, p. 68). It is important noting that goodness of fit levels

⁴ As many other variables of social networks—hyperlinks networks often follow a power-law distribution (Barnett, 2011, p. 79). An important characteristic of power law systems is that popular subjects feature extremely disproportionate popularity gains, likely causing that few popular subjects are as popular as all others combined. To prevent outweighing, I transform the weights by $w^{(1/\alpha)}$, whereas α is derived from a fitted power-law distribution using R's *power.law.fit* (Csárdi & Nepusz, 2006). In case of the Greek debt discourse, α is about 1.67 ($p = 0.607$) and in case of the migration discussion α is 1.69 ($p = 0.138$). The p values indicate that the null-hypothesis (data drawn from alternative distribution) is rejected in both cases. As an alternative to the transformation, one might also use rank scores of participant's popularity as weights and would yield virtually the same positions.

are purely technical, substantively blind, and inform nothing about the compatibility of a theory with the PCoA configuration or about its interpretability (Borg et al., 2013). In order to assess the validity of results, robustness, replicability, and (substantial) interpretability of calculated coordinates inform better than goodness of fit indicators. Thus, I assess in detail, whether both identified principal coordinates represent unidimensional ideological spaces of the public discourses under study. For this purpose, I perform several assessments and robustness tests such as external data consultations, subsample tests, and case comparison.

First, my data feature several reference points that offer opportunity for external validation. For instance, researchers analyzed the ideological stances of the largest German quality newspapers finding that they cover almost the entire political spectrum (Donsbach, Wolling, & Blomberg, 1996; Eilders, 2002). According to Eilders, *Die Welt*, *die Bild*, *Frankfurter Allgemeine*, and *Focus* defend all a right-conservative position, whereas the left wing was covered by *Tageszeitung (Taz)*, *Süddeutsche Zeitung*, *Frankfurter Rundschau*, *Die Zeit*, as well as *Spiegel*. This pattern accurately mirrors in the PCoA results for both discourses (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Ideological Segregation of Top 20 Traditional Media Outlets

a) Refugee Discourse

b) Greek Debt Discourse

Second, it is possible to validate the substantial meaning of PCoA results by looking at the position of online sites of politicians, factions, and parties. As figure 1 reveals, also these positions correspond to the expected ideological stance having the Left (*Die Linke*), the Greens (*die Grünen*), the Social Democrats (*SPD*) in the left wing, and the Christian Democratic Union (*CDU*) and the Christian Social Union (*CSU*) on the right wing of the axis. Corresponding to the expectations, the Alternative for Germany (*AfD*), the National Democratic Party (*NPD*), and the Freedom Party of Austria (*FPÖ*) were located in the radical right of the political spectrum.

Figure 1: Ideological Segregation of Top 20 Traditional Media Outlets

While mean positions of party outlets presented in Figure 2 fit expectations, there are a few remarkable positional shifts between the discourses. The German government party *CDU* of Chancellor Angela Merkel made the largest shift. As I will elaborate in more detail below, this shift is adequately to explain by case contexts. During the period of this study, *CDU* took in one discourse (Greek debt discourse) a firm conservative position and in the other (refugee discourse) rather a left-wing position. Hence, the *CDU*'s shift in the placement in Figure 2 illustrates the strength of the method to map the political positions context-sensitively.

The comparison of ideological positions between the two discourses is the basis for the last robustness test. When the mapping performs well and in the absence of discourse-specific reasons, outlets should obtain relatively constant ideological positions. More than three hundred media outlets took part in both discourses. For them I found a considerable correlation (Pearson coefficient: 0.59) in their principal coordinates.

Figure 3: Ideological Segregation: Correlation Between Discourses

Figure 3 reveals that most observations with large residuals are located at the right-conservative pole. However, also the center reveals some striking examples of deviants. Most fundamental is the ideological shift of the *Sächsische Zeitung* (*sz-online.de*) located in figure 3 in the southeastern part. To understand the shift of this particular newspaper, it is important to know that it is economically related to the *SPD* (Heimeier, 2013, p. 282). As a government party, the *SPD* rather took a left-wing stance in one case (refugee discourse), and it defended the firm austerity-first position of the *CDU* (refugee discourse) in the other case. Ideological position of the editors and not a methodical flaw is a plausible explanation for this particular deviation.

After scanning the 1,724 coordinates of all the online sites considered, I find only a handful sites assigned with coordinates that were diametric to expectations (See

appendix 0 for the full list). One of the wrongly placed online sites was the Facebook site *fb.com/rote-antifa-front* cultivated by a group from the radical left with the maxim to condemn fascism in Germany. Actually, in my data there is only one genuine tweet with a hyperlink to this Facebook group. Yet, this tweet was then retweeted 76 times among right-wing users with an allegation that the group receives financial support from the local government. Consequently, the mapping method assigns the Facebook page “wrongly” to the right camp. While this example clearly shows that a viral tweet might distort a placement, it also shows, vice versa, that in the majority of the cases, the method works well. All other 26 *Antifa* labeled online sites in my dataset obtained a clear left coordinate. In contrast to my initial expectation, misplacements for unpopular social-media outlets are rather unlikely, since they tend to have only a narrow readership and enjoy low awareness beyond the own ideological camp.

Overall, external validation, the robustness over subsamples, the rarity of counterintuitive cases, the high correlation rate between the discourses, and the awareness that context conditions explain a significant part of deviation gives strong confidence in the method to identify ideological positions of online actors that participate in public discourses.

How Segregated Are Social Media Discourses

I. Refugee Discourse

I analyze by two case studies the segregation of social-media discourses and compare them to the discourses lead by traditional media. The first case study is the discourse about the refugee crisis that hit Europe hardly in the summer 2015. The situation escalated when an extraordinary number of asylum seekers arrived in Europe. The severe situation at the borders of the European Union and on the popular migration routes inside the Union triggered—foremost in the eastern German states—anti-refugee manifestations as well as incendiary attacks on asylum centers. In response to the right-wing protests, moderate or left activists imitated an outstanding counter-

movement: citizens, traditional media, and politicians kept expressing solidarity with migrants in need and stood up against racism and right wing violence. The German government (in particular *SPD* and most of the *CDU*) strongly supported the solidarity movement. In a startling move, Chancellor Angela Merkel declared Germany to receive a couple of hundreds of refugees stranded in Hungary.

I now turn to the data and analyze coherence of the social-media discourse during the refugee Discourse. In order to assess polarization, I focus on the frequency distribution of identified social-media outlets. I consider a discourse as segregated when media outlets are distributed in a multipolar way. In contrast, I consider a discourse as non-segregated when outlet's distribution is unipolar.

According to this definition, figure 4 reveals that the social-media discourse during the refugee discourse was highly segregated, since most social media are located either in the (radical) right or in the moderate-left camp. The lack of social-media outlets in the political middle suggests that hardly any social-media outlets appeal to both camps simultaneously. I take this result as a strong indication that the social media failed to integrate divergent ideological perspectives in single forums in this specific discourse. Instead, the findings support the hypothesis of digital sceptics claiming that people prefer to interact with likeminded people.

As claimed above, the assessment of the hypothesis that segregation is a characteristic of the social-media discourse requires a comparison with the traditional media outlets. Although extracted by exactly the same method, the traditional media outlets are unipolar distributed, which indicates that traditional media perform much better when it comes to provide content appealing to various ideological camps.

Figure 4: Ideologic segregation of media outlets in the refugee discourse in German speaking countries

Not surprisingly, the organization that played the major role in the right-wing social-media movement was the Grassroots movement *Pegida*. *Pegida*⁵ is a right wing islamophobic grassroots movement that has organized regular demonstrations against immigrants and a “decay of German values.” The supporters of *Pegida* are not only motivated by the fear of negative economic, social, and cultural consequences of immigration, they are also dissatisfied by the media and politics as well as of defamatory statements made by left-liberal citizens (Dostal, 2015; Hans, Herold, & Schäller, 2015; Patzelt, 2015). Not less than eight mapped online sites entail the name of the organization. Also the URLs of other outlets in the right-wing reveals close ties to the *Pegida* movement, as they refer to well-known themes.⁶

On the other side of the political spectrum, the radical left, too, makes extensive usage of social media. The map entails not less than 26 online resources from *Antifa*

⁵ *Pegida* is an abbreviation for the German phrase of “patriotic Europeans against the islamization of the occident.”

⁶ Such as *Heimat, Deutschland, Germania, Volk, Patrioten, Bürgerstimme, Opposition, Widerstand, Aufwachen, Staatsstreich, Volksbetrug, Sezession, Behördenstress, and Unbequeme Wahrheit*. Hereby, the *Pegida* movement turns out to be an example for a counter-public as described by Lincoln Dahlberg (2007, p. 838). Dahlberg discusses a solid empirical body evidencing the prominent usage of social media and other digital technology to support the formation and maintenance of counter-discourses as antagonists to the hegemonic reading.

factions. *Antifa* is a term used in the extreme left wing for anti-fascists, anti-nationalistic, and anti-racist groups (Backes, 2008). Many of the other URLs in this ideological region reveal strong relation to the *Antifa* movement or share its goal to condemn fascism in Germany.

The social media located in the middle of the plot reveal a strong dedication to affirmative actions geared to improve the situations of refugees. Many of the well-known NGOs such as *amnesty international*, *Médecins Sans Frontières*, *Caritas*, and *Red Cross* are located in this area. Many other online sites in this area clearly follow altruistic goals. Their URLs refer to the intention to achieve better legal, medical, and housing conditions of refugees.⁷ These outlets impressively show that opposing the mainstream reading is not the only intention of social-media usage. Here, the activist's values and goals were in considerable compliance with government and majority of traditional media.

To sum up, the refugee discourse is an illustrative case for the polarization hypothesis defended by Cass Sunstein. In comparison to traditional media, the social-media sphere is highly segregated along ideological camps.

II. Greek Debt Discourse

The second case concerns the Greek government-debt crisis that dominated political agenda in the first half of the summer of 2015. In June and July, we witnessed a long and intensive negotiation between the Greek government party *Syriza* and the lender institutions represented by the European Commission, the European central bank, and the International Monetary Fund (nicknamed as the *Trojka*). The negotiations aimed to prevent a bankruptcy of the Greek state, which was unable to pay short-term obligations and thus needed either a debt cut or an extension of the repayment terms. Yet, the German government (consisting of the three party *CDU*, *CSU*, and *SPD*) was

⁷ Symptomatical terms are «*wie kann ich helfen*», «*refugees welcome*», «*Menschenwürdig*», «*Recht auf Menschenrecht*», «*Aktion-Mensch*», «*ich helfe jetzt*», «*refugeevoices*», «*Wohllollen*», «*Aktion Zivilcourage*», «*Asylfakten*», «*Refugeesupport*», «*Migration Info*», «*Blogger für Flüchtlinge*», «*Refugeehelper*», «*Recht-auf-menschenrecht*», and so on.

not willing to give way for a compromise as long as Greece refuses to conduct further austerity measures to increase the competitiveness of their country. A majority of German citizens supported the firm position of their government. However, a significant opposition arose at the left wing. Some left-wing activists accused the government to pursue purely selfish and myopic goals (i.e., attempting to put out of charge the left-wing Government in Athens to continue a neo-liberal agenda). Many of them did not believe that the demanded austerity reforms would improve Greece's situation. Other activists pledged to put aside economic considerations and requested unconditional help for the Greek people in need. What the left-wing opposition had in common is that they claimed that traditional media (in particular the public owned television channels) were biased and did not seriously take into account policy alternatives to austerity.⁸

Turning to the data, figure 5 reveals a left tendency in the social-media sphere. After scanning the list of the URLs on the left side (see appendix 0), it becomes clear that the left side consists out of an amalgam of political groups such as anti-capitalism (e.g., *marx21.de*), EU-enthusiasm (e.g., *lostineu.eu*), Keynesianism (e.g., *stopausterity.eu*), humanism (e.g., *hilfsaktion-gegen-hunger-in-griechenland.de*) and many outlets of epistemically oriented research communities.⁹ The social media movement peaked at the same ideological positions where the blog of Greek's finance minister Yannis Varoufakis is located. The social media appear to have taken a mediating role between traditional media and the position of Greeks finance minister.

⁸ Many prominent voices perceived media coverage as biased. For instance, Jürgen Habermas («Habermas: Warum Merkels Griechenland-Politik ein Fehler ist», *Süddeutsche Zeitung*, June 22, 2015), Matthias Thiele («Talkshow-Kritik: Völlige Einseitigkeit und ein nationaler Wir-Diskurs», *Telepolis*, July 29, 2015), Stefan Winterbauer («Das Grexit Drama und der Bankrott unserer Medienrepublik», *Meedia*, June 25, 2015), Gesine Schwan («Irre Griechen? Wie viel Demokratie verträgt Europa?», *Monitor/WDR*, July 2, 2015), and Cornelia Ernst («Zum Abschalten», *Neues Deutschland*, July 3, 2015.)

⁹ In this area, some popular media are project-syndicate.org, globalresearch.ca, wirtschaftundgesellschaft.de, flussbeck-economics.de, verfassungsblog.de, internet-law.de, lawblog.de, blog.arbeit-wirtschaft.at, ipg-journal.de, oekonomenstimme.org, transform-network.net, carta.info, and socialeurope.eu.

Most importantly, figure 5 reveals a unipolar frequency distribution of social-media outlets that does not support the hypothesis that significant segregation took place. There is no indication that segregation within social-media sphere was higher than within the traditional media sphere. Apparently, segregation is not a necessary consequence of social-media engagement.

Nevertheless, figure 5 hints at another type of segregation. Instead of segregation within, segregation took place between the spheres. The plotted structure of the public discourse shows that the reports of traditional media organizations tend to appeal stronger to conservative readers.⁸ The left dominance within social media is remarkable, because it contrasts to the offline world, in which a large majority of citizens supported the government’s position. This imbalance suggests that people who felt excluded by traditional media are among the most frequent users of social media.

Figure 4: Ideologic segregation of media outlets in the Greek debt discourse in German speaking countries

Overall, the observed data suggests that social media strengthen the voice of the anti-austerity position inadequately covered by traditional media. Yet, the results do

not indicate that degree of segregation differs between social media and traditional media outlets.

Discussion

The two case studies draw an ambiguous picture on social-media segregation. Surely, there are occasions in which segregation of social media clearly surpass segregation of traditional media, such as the right-conservative outlets in the refugee discourse. Yet in other situations, social media can play a different role. For instance, they can form the counterpart of an ideologically homogenous traditional media sphere (Greece Debt Discourse) or they could provide a platform for a grassroots engagement that is in surprising ideological alignment with traditional media and political elitists (e.g. “refugees welcome”-movement). It is likely that these engagement patterns are only few of many potential faces of social-media engagement (L. Dahlberg, 2011).

Scholars give various reasons why empirical findings on segregation or polarization hypothesis are inconsistent. For instance, scholars claim that the harmful effects of echo chamber are overestimated, since participants have “escape routes”, since even in echo chambers dissenting views are expressed (Brundidge, 2010; Garrett & Stroud, 2014; O’Hara & Stevens, 2015, p. 17). Other scholars shed light on specific context conditions, suggesting that group polarization only occurs when members of an echo chamber have long-term ties (Grönlund, Herne, & Setälä, 2015; C. R. Sunstein, 2002, p. 180). Other scholars deny that the cyberspace is as segregated as presumed, especially when one compares it to the communication networks in the offline world (Gentzkow & Shapiro, 2011). The present study partly supports this last explanation. Apparently, not in all occasions, segregation within social media trumps segregation within traditional media.

What do these results mean for assessment of democratic evaluation of social media? In recent years, the normative reading on media segregation changed, as voices increased emphasizing the emancipatory, epistemic, participatory, and mobilizing

potential of segregation. Some of these voices stress the respective opportunities for lower resource groups as training grounds for agitational activities (Lincoln Dahlberg, 2007; Fraser, 1992). Minority groups might use social media to better achieve a more equal standing of positions (Karpowitz, Raphael, & Hammond, 2009). Mutz (2006) adds that the confrontation with different views has a strong demotivating effect on political participation. Hence, it is tremendously likely that segregated online discourses might better pursue not only the equal standing but also the participatory goal of democracy. Furthermore, a segregated public discourse—through elevating the level of contestation—might promote epistemic benefits, when it helps to correct or publicize blind-spots or group think failures within a hegemonic discourse (Bächtiger, 2010; Manin, 2005; Mansbridge et al., 2012, p. 18). In the view of these considerations, social media do not constitute a serious threat for democracy, in particular, when one considers that segregation is only one among many feasible ends of social-media usage.

However, there is an aspect in my findings that may be thought provoking. Recently, many scholars emphasized the mediating role of traditional media, which is supposed to counter social-media segregation by integrative coverage (Sunstein 2001). Yet, the present studies suggest that traditional media are not in all cases able to act as “general interest intermediaries.” When traditional media have a clear political stance (as in the Greece Debt discourse) or when they lose credibility in one ideological camp (as it happens in the refugee discourse) then the mediating role of traditional media is questionable. Such situations clearly represent a challenge for democracy (Lincoln Dahlberg, 2007, p. 839).

Conclusion

The academic literature provides theoretical and empirical support for the idea that the extension of public discourses through social media tends to promote ideological segregation within public discourses. In order to assess this hypothesis, I introduced an innovative Twitter-based technique, which sheds light on the structure

of large, dynamic, and heterogeneous public discourses. Based on this technique, I analyzed the structure of two online discourses – the refugee and Greek debt crisis - in German-speaking countries in 2015. Remarkably, I find that segregation was present only in one of the two case studies—namely in the context of the refugee discourse. This means that there is not something like a “general law” stating that social-media usage always leads to the segregation of public discourses; instead, context-specific factors seem to play a role. While more research is needed to identify such contextual factors, the results of this study puts a question mark on digital sceptics’ arguments that social media inevitably produces centrifugal tendencies.

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Appendix

I. Table 1: Statistics of Collected Tweets

	Refugee Discourse	Greek Debt Discourse
Collection period	Aug 10 – Sep 10, 2015	Jun 15 – Aug 06, 2015
Number of tweets	500'000	500,000
Peak day	Aug 28, 2015 (34,644 tweets)	Jul 12, 2015 (39'543 tweets)
Twitter users	89,310	88,783
User references (@)	356,107	282,616
Topic references (#)	291,517	279,166
Retweets	297,741	213,801
Tweets with links	69.3%	71.3%
Number of valid links	338,092	356,381
Unique hyperlink targets	100,241	98,190
Unique outlets (providers of spread utterances)	7,887	5,732
Coded outlets (number of spreaders \geq 5)	1,670	1,209
Considered outlets (Social Media, Traditional Media, Privileged Actors)	1,052	672

II. Table 2: Ideological Positions in the Refugee Discourse

Social Media Outlets in the Refugee Discourse	Left	Center	Right
proasyl.de	.		
indymedia.org	.		
fb.com/nonueglda	.		
dresden-nazifrei.com	.		
endstation-rechts.de	.		
eams.blogspot.eu	.		
fb.com/dresden.stellt.sich.quer	.		
netz-gegen-nazis.de	.		
zusammenschmeissen.de	.		
dokmz.wordpress.com	.		
bnr.de	.		
africavenir.org	.		
fb.com/refugeeswelcomele	.		
addn.me	.		
agv.blogspot.de	.		
jungle-world.com	.		
wordpress.antifa-essen.de	.		
fb.com/hamburger-buendnis-gegen-rechts	.		
recherche-nord.com	.		
beobachternews.de	.		
aa170.noblogs.org	.		
fb.com/antifaunion	.		
fluechtlingsrat-lpz.org	.		
kulturbuero-sachsen.de	.		
attenzione-photo.com	.		
publikative.org	.		
raa-sachsen.de	.		
jg-stadtmitte.de	.		
refugeeswelcomepad.wordpress.com	.		
fb.com/zumsaru	.		
socialcenter4all.blackblogs.org	.		
antifainfoblatt.de	.		
so36.de	.		
nordstadtblogger.de	.		
refugeeswelcomeaberauch.blogspot.eu	.		
fb.com/gritt.kutscher	.		
task.noblogs.org	.		
aikoeln.blogspot.eu	.		
migazin.de	.		
akantifaac.blogspot.de	.		
fb.com/in.svens.welt	.		
rechtesland.de	.		
antifa-ak.org	.		
enssq.blogspot.eu	.		
refugeeswelcomedo.noblogs.org	.		
antifapinneberg.blogspot.de	.		
brunnen7.org	.		
jule.linxnet.de	.		
antifacafedortmund.blogspot.eu	.		
endstation-rechts-bayern.de	.		
fb.com/afnpsxn	.		
akubiz.de	.		
fb.com/antifaessen	.		
fb.com/hipsterantifagreifswald	.		
statewatch.org	.		
afaerz.blogspot.de	.		
fb.com/nohogesa	.		
oacb.noblogs.org	.		
fb.com/dresden fuer alle	.		
rav.de	.		
buendnis-neukoelln.de	.		
festivalgegenrassismus.wordpress.com	.		
hpd.de	.		
redside.tk	.		
wuppertal2015.blackblogs.org	.		
goodbyedeutschland.blogspot.eu	.		
deutschlandliebwaterland.wordpress.com	.		
ignaz.blogspot.de	.		
antifa-kiel.org	.		
fb.com/heidenu-hoert-zu	.		
fb.com/wir-sind-viele	.		
icrc.org	.		
martingommel.tumblr.com	.		
asyl-in-not.org	.		
netzwerk-gegen-rechts.org	.		
trotz allem.blogspot.de	.		
aida-archiv.de	.		
lowerclassmag.com	.		
refugeeswelcome.blogspot.eu	.		
seehilfe.com	.		
kompass.antira.info	.		
antifa-frankfurt.org	.		
eschweiler-juden.de	.		

Social Media Outlets in the Refugee Discourse	Left	Center	Right
fb.com/dezentralisierungjetzt	.		
fb.com/nopegidastuttgart	.		
autonome-antifa.org	.		
hrbruns.com	.		
oplatz.net	.		
psd-zukunftspreis.de	.		
rosalux.de	.		
antifa-lg-ue.org	.		
fb.com/lutz.richter.9	.		
grilleau.blogspot.com	.		
sechel.it	.		
nichteinentag.tk	.		
antifa.riox.eu	.		
linkespankow.wordpress.com	.		
hackelclub590.de	.		
gewantifa.blogspot.eu	.		
ichhelfe.jetzt	.		
mut-gegen-rechte-gewalt.de	.		
ruhrbarone.de	.		
fb.com/nonazinet	.		
hautab.wordpress.com	.		
interventionistische-linke.org	.		
menschen-wuerdig.org	.		
patrick-gensing.info	.		
compact.de	.		
thueringenrechtsausssen.wordpress.com	.		
fb.com/azaachenbleibt	.		
fb.com/mfgnoffizielleseite	.		
blog.17vier.de	.		
fb.com/interventionistische.linke.luebeck	.		
stadtkontext.de	.		
edu.migration-audio-archiv.de	.		
antifa-nordost.org	.		
fb.com/pegidawatch	.		
rosenheimnazifrei.blogspot.de	.		
fb.com/aluhut.fuer.ken.site	.		
pizzapunk.net	.		
antifainfo.de	.		
fb.com/demowatch.muc	.		
fb.com/nolagerfreiburg	.		
stopasylaw.blogspot.eu	.		
atfjena.blogspot.eu	.		
azconni.de	.		
fb.com/claudiusholler	.		
zvr-online.com	.		
drksachsen.de	.		
quimera.noblogs.org	.		
campus-asyl.de	.		
fb.com/aikoeln	.		
notalone.blogspot.eu	.		
antifalinkemuenster.blogspot.de	.		
nadir.org	.		
navdem.com	.		
nazistopp-nuernberg.de	.		
stefan-niggemeier.de	.		
blaetter.de	.		
darbarnenover.aftonbladet.se	.		
fb.com/treffpunkt.asyl.bochum	.		
fb.com/dresdenpegidafrei	.		
adfc-muenchen.de	.		
amnesty.de	.		
antifakoeln.noblogs.org	.		
christian-ditsch.photoshelter.com	.		
gedenkkongress.de	.		
kritisch-lesen.de	.		
bordermonitoring.eu	.		
fb.com/refugees-welcome-info	.		
24mmjournalism.com	.		
fb.com/drksachsen	.		
fb.com/thomas.schmidinger	.		
syndikalismus.wordpress.com	.		
amadeu-antonio-stiftung.de	.		
digitalcourage.de	.		
prinzessinnenreporter.de	.		
zumsaru.de	.		
berlin-gegen-nazis.de	.		
piekabache.blogspot.de	.		
buntesamt.blogspot.com	.		
news-photo.de	.		
antifa-berlin.info	.		
deinehappybox.de	.		
fb.com/refugeeswelcome20357	.		
fb.com/wientvorg	.		
katja-kipping.de	.		
refugeevoices.de	.		
fb.com/dresdenoffenundtolerant	.		

Social Media Outlets in the Refugee Discourse	Left	Center	Right
abgeordnetenwatch.de			
gegenrechts.koeln			
nerdcore.de			
antinazi.wordpress.com			
hamm.noblogs.org			
asyl.at			
jesus.de			
aktion-arschloch.de			
antifaunion.blogspot.de			
arpu.blogspot.eu			
adoptrevolution.org			
vvn-bda.de			
fb.com/leftreportberlin			
fb.com/widerstandheidenau			
kritischerfrieden.blogspot.de			
md.freifunk.net			
fb.com/meißen-hört-zu			
freelens.com			
rucksackspenden.wordpress.com			
netzpolitik.org			
abcug.hu			
krawallkroete.wordpress.com			
antifagp.blogspot.eu			
chrisgaer.wordpress.com			
mosaik-blog.at			
radikale-linke.net			
schmetterlingssammlung.net			
keeptalkingreece.com			
blaulicht.antifa.riox.eu			
fb.com/butz-lachmann			
ak36.blogspot.de			
fb.com/meißen-watch			
runandroll.de			
fb.com/fpoeticker			
kopfkompass.de			
fb.com/donations-for-röszke-refugee-camp...			
medico.de			
viewsoftheworld.net			
welcome.blogspot.de			
antifabochum.noblogs.org			
refugeehackathon.de			
hackathon.wien			
fb.com/dietmar.bauer1			
wohlwollen.com			
fb.com/derw23			
hiksch.com			
lauterbautzner.eu			
achtermai.org			
hackerstolz.de			
crowdcounting.de			
antifaaufbautue.blogspot.de			
chronikle.org			
rheinneckarblog.de			
aktion-zivilcourage.de			
kas.de			
fb.com/keinort			
schantall-und-scharia.de			
fb.com/interventionistischelinke			
sehnsuchtsort.de			
fragdenstaat.de			
asylfakten.de			
internet-law.de			
muschelschloss.wordpress.com			
siempreffm.blogspot.de			
amerika21.de			
mediendienst-integration.de			
refugeeguide.de			
refugeesupport.blogspot.de			
graswurzel.tv			
perlen-aus-freital.tumblr.com			
doyoudare.de			
maedchenmannschaft.net			
fb.com/freiheitfuerpaul			
neusprech.org			
polizeimensch.de			
preiselbauer.de			
kraftfuttermischwerk.de			
labournet.de			
boell.de			
gedankensex.de			
dievilla.at			
fb.com/bildunxfem			
blog.campact.de			
fb.com/neudeutscherstumpfsinn			
wemove.eu			
womenundersiegeproject.org			

Social Media Outlets in the Refugee Discourse	Left	Center	Right
fb.com/1ab.ffm			.
staublos.ch			.
agpolitischetheorie.de			.
roteskreuz.at			.
mlpd.de			.
netzpiloten.de			.
migration-info.de			.
seeroiberjenny.wordpress.com			.
aktion-mensch.de			.
evangelisch.de			.
machtelite.wordpress.com			.
twickster.wordpress.com			.
blogger-fuer-fluechtlinge.de			.
ninabrnada.com			.
bilblog.de			.
fb.com/martin.sonneborn			.
hellersdorfhilft.wordpress.com			.
refugeesemancipation.com			.
joergrupp.de			.
antirepression.noblogs.org			.
misereor.de			.
papiertiger.noblogs.org			.
fb.com/heidenau-ist-bunt			.
gefuechtet.de			.
drlima.net			.
reflektierter-bengel.de			.
guedesweiler.wordpress.com			.
shehadistan.com			.
wie-kann-ich-helfen.info			.
fckfpoe.tumblr.com			.
refugee.actionmap.eu			.
spreblick.com			.
bo-alternativ.de			.
caritas-international.de			.
papaleaks.de			.
verfassungsblog.de			.
hrw.org			.
antifainternational.tumblr.com			.
denkwerkstattblog.net			.
omnipolis.com			.
valentin.blogsport.de			.
lebenshaus-alb.de			.
uiuuuuuuuuui.de			.
meinparlament.at			.
thesyriacampaign.org			.
iom.int			.
schleckysilberstein.com			.
trueten.de			.
afaarea.blogsport.de			.
ipg-journal.de			.
refugeehelper.net			.
fb.com/migrationaidhungary			.
sprachlog.de			.
essen-stellt-sich-quer.de			.
nichts-gegen-juden.de			.
ourstoriescologne.tumblr.com			.
diekuchenbaeckerin.wordpress.com			.
fb.com/michel.reimon			.
herzdamengeschichten.de			.
jungundnaiv-podcast.de			.
fluechtlinge-willkommen.at			.
recht-auf-menschenrecht.de			.
msf.at			.
attac.at			.
unsere-zeitung.at			.
aussengedanken.de			.
ichbinkeinrassistaber.tumblr.com			.
johanneshuber.me			.
oeh.ac.at			.
parisax.de			.
alpbach.org			.
medi-bild.de			.
robinsurbanlifestories.wordpress.com			.
experimentselfbstversorgung.net			.
kub-berlin.org			.
fb.com/barbara.maier.376			.
globalcitizen.org			.
jugendhilfeportal.de			.
fb.com/simonbeeckofficial			.
umstandslos.com			.
zeitenhund.com			.
cagle.com			.
civaka-azad.org			.
pingumania.wordpress.com			.
fb.com/8maibuendnis			.
hallespektrum.de			.

Social Media Outlets in the Refugee Discourse	Left	Center	Right
migration-online.de		.	
blog.kiko-slevents.de		.	
diefreiheitsliebe.de		.	
fb.com/krautreporter		.	
anonymous-austria.com		.	
jef.de		.	
kofi2go.wordpress.com		.	
bloedermichel.web-xxl.com		.	
derwandel.at		.	
spiegelfechter.com		.	
foraus.ch		.	
nachtkritik.de		.	
wrint.de		.	
nachdenkseiten.de		.	
durchgezacht.wordpress.com		.	
euobserver.com		.	
humor-kamensky.sk		.	
lobby16.org		.	
sos-childrevillages.org		.	
9gag.com		.	
brightsblog.wordpress.com		.	
menschenrechtserklaerung.de		.	
stuttman-karikaturen.de		.	
erzdioezese-wien.at		.	
project-syndicate.org		.	
welthungerhilfe.de		.	
argudiss.de		.	
sos-kinderdoerfer.de		.	
zwanzigtausendfrauen.at		.	
aktion-deutschland-hilft.de		.	
fb.com/niggemeier		.	
stopptierechten.at		.	
hintergrund.de		.	
infosperber.ch		.	
fluechtlinge-willkommen.de		.	
grafmix.wordpress.com		.	
rationalgalerie.de		.	
theuropean.de		.	
blogrebell.de		.	
fb.com/fastforwardhannover		.	
frauenrechte.de		.	
redcross.ch		.	
gehörtgebloggt.wordpress.com		.	
lawblog.de		.	
paraflows.at		.	
diesubstanz.at		.	
amnesty.ch		.	
asyl.net		.	
liberale.de		.	
flaneurgedichte.blogspot.com		.	
fluechtlingshilfe.caritas.de		.	
blog.drk.de		.	
oekonomenstimme.org		.	
switzerland-asylum.strikingly.com		.	
blog.fefe.de		.	
parlament.neos.eu		.	
fb.com/fluechtlingshilfeohne Grenzen		.	
drk.de		.	
youngcaritas.ruhr		.	
caritas.at		.	
journal21.ch		.	
pixeloekonom.de		.	
islamiq.de		.	
broeckers.com		.	
w2eu.info		.	
openpetition.de		.	
eine-zeitung.net		.	
fluchthelfer.in		.	
diakonie-katastrophenhilfe.de		.	
eichstaettweltweit.wordpress.com		.	
0x0a.li		.	
nachrichtenspiegel.de		.	
fb.com/rmisik		.	
netzfrauen.org		.	
proverfassung.de		.	
antjesievers.wordpress.com		.	
patriotische-plattform.de		.	
globalresearch.ca		.	
polenum.com		.	
radio-utopie.de		.	
danisch.de		.	
christoph-hörstel-wwb.de		.	
uncut-news.ch		.	
blauerbote.com		.	
freiheit-toleranz.de		.	
stop-ttip.org		.	

Social Media Outlets in the Refugee Discourse	Left	Center	Right
bodenseenews.wordpress.com			•
terragermania.com			•
pinksliberal.wordpress.com			•
filmdenken.de			•
wissensmanufaktur.net			•
pflueger.org			•
marialourdesblog.com			•
deutschland-2-0.blogspot.com			•
politikversagen.net			•
pravda-tv.com			•
bayern-depesche.de			•
politaia.org			•
propagandaschau.wordpress.com			•
cep.eu			•
statusquo-news.de			•
jasminrevolution.wordpress.com			•
unbequemewahrheit2014.wordpress.com			•
nachgerichtet.is			•
cora-stephan.blogspot.com			•
refugeair.org			•
ejbron.wordpress.com			•
daserwachendervalkyrjar.wordpress.com			•
wernibehtel.wordpress.com			•
morgenschau.blogspot.com			•
ceiberweiber.myblog.de			•
new.euro-med.dk			•
der-dritte-weg.info			•
staatszeugen.de			•
treueundehre.wordpress.com			•
behoerdenstress13.com			•
dubistkeinpersonal.wordpress.com			•
kritisches-netzwerk.de			•
schreibfreiheit.eu			•
audiatur-online.ch			•
brd-gameover.de			•
pressejournalismus.com			•
politik-im-spiegel.de			•
kulfoldihirek.com			•
zeit-zum-aufwachen.blogspot.com			•
nicht-feminist.de			•
sichtplatz.de			•
krisenfrei.de			•
mzw-widerstand.com			•
fb.com/pegida.nrw.offiziell			•
fb.com/i.bearth			•
sachsen-depesche.de			•
fb.com/kayacahit			•
gerhardschneider.at			•
fb.com/gugemapegida			•
fb.com/marco.m.hober			•
helmutmueller.wordpress.com			•
hinter-der-fichte.blogspot.com			•
meinungsfreiheit24.wordpress.com			•
grenzhelfer.in			•
pegida-muenchen.org			•
themuslimissue.wordpress.com			•
fb.com/fuer.die.heimat			•
rechte-muenchen.de			•
guidograndt.wordpress.com			•
heerlagerderheiligen.wordpress.com			•
ortneronline.at			•
asylcafe.com			•
sezession.de			•
pro-deutschland-online.de			•
hallemax.com			•
geolitico.de			•
haunebu7.wordpress.com			•
charismatismus.wordpress.com			•
hannig-rechtsanwaelte.de			•
arbeitskreis-n.su			•
nicolaus-fest.de			•
sciencefiles.org			•
koppbackend.de			•
anderweltonline.com			•
inhr.net			•
korrektheiten.com			•
die-anmerkung.blogspot.com			•
erstaunlich.at			•
pamelageller.com			•
selberdenkenhilftimmer.wordpress.com			•
npannn.wordpress.com			•
qpress.de			•
alles-schallundrauch.blogspot.com			•
derhonigmannsagt.wordpress.com			•
fb.com/priznajem.hrvtasam			•
behoerdenstress.de			•

Social Media Outlets in the Refugee Discourse	Left	Center	Right
staseve.eu			.
rolandtichy.de			.
volksbetrugpunktnet.wordpress.com			.
gegen-hartz.de			.
neuland.mustermann.org			.
fb.com/identitaere			.
fb.com/lutz-bachmann			.
killerbeesagt.wordpress.com			.
achgut.com			.
buergerstimme.com			.
fb.com/sebastian.loewenherz			.
alternative-heidelberg.de			.
sicherungsblog.wordpress.com			.
andreas-unterberger.at			.
maximiliankrah.wordpress.com			.
fredalanmedforth.blogspot.com			.
fb.com/pegida.daebritz			.
opensocietyfoundations.org			.
bff-frankfurt.de			.
fatalistsuleaks.wordpress.com			.
thegatewaypundit.com			.
der-kleine-akif.de			.
fb.com/joekerrl			.
freiraum-magazin.com			.
fluechtlingsticker.wordpress.com			.
halbpfosten.blogspot.com			.
wiedenroth-karikatur.de			.
marbec14.wordpress.com			.
conservo.wordpress.com			.
fb.com/rote-anifafa-front-raf-384528924929236			.
fb.com/legida.eu			.
fb.com/udoboenstrup			.
rundertischdggf.wordpress.com			.
fb.com/pegidadreilaendereck			.
brd-schwindel.org			.
indexexpurgatorius.wordpress.com			.
heplev.wordpress.com			.
fb.com/pegidavdresden			.
deutschelobby.com			.
fb.com/anonymous.kollektiv			.
zukunfiskinder.org			.
dortmundecho.org			.
meinungspack.de			.
legida.eu			.
blaulicht-paparazzo.de			.
mzw-widerstand.info			.
babykaust.de			.
jihadwatch.org			.
denken-macht-frei.info			.
klartext.la			.
fb.com/villain051			.
juergensaesser.wordpress.com			.
widerstand.info			.
fb.com/iris.buecker			.
messerattacke.wordpress.com			.
petraaab.blogspot.com			.
fb.com/afd.supporter			.
blu-news.org			.
zeitgeisterjagd.de			.
einwanderungskritik.de			.
fb.com/roman.aland			.
quotenqueen.wordpress.com			.
opposition24.de			.
fb.com/usa2028883144			.
michael-mannheimer.net			.
journalistenwatch.com			.
fb.com/adelbertostertag			.
freiepatrioten.de			.
mmnews.de			.
staatsstreich.at			.
pi-news.net			.

III. Table 3: Ideological Positions in the Greece Debt Discourse

Social Media Outlets in the Greece Debt Discourse	Left	Center	Right
fb.com/srddorf	•		
linksjugend-solid-koeln.blogspot.com	•		
linksunten.indimedia.org	•		
mlwerke.de	•		
fb.com/blockupy.europe	•		
change4all.eu	•		
blockupy.org	•		
stefan-niggemeier.de	•		
mosaik-blog.at	•		
fb.com/revoltgermany	•		
marx21.de	•		
soli-komitee-wuppertal.mobi	•		
griechenlandsolidaritaetffm.wordpress.com	•		
solidarische-moderne.de	•		
pltxffm.tumblr.com	•		
umsganze.org	•		
beobachternews.de	•		
rosalux.de	•		
indymedia.org	•		
vdaee.de	•		
heathwoodpress.com	•		
fb.com/attactip	•		
stop-ttip.org	•		
labournet.de	•		
prinzessinnenreporter.de	•		
misik.at		•	
wurfbude.wordpress.de		•	
florange.eu		•	
transform-network.net		•	
blog.campact.de		•	
proasyl.de		•	
migazin.de		•	
jungle-world.com		•	
flassbeck-economics.de		•	
stuetzle.cc		•	
hiksch.com		•	
wolfgangmichal.de		•	
berlingazette.de		•	
lowerclassmag.com		•	
attac.de		•	
prinzchaos.wordpress.com		•	
die-anstifter.de		•	
fb.com/rmisik		•	
cit-consult.de		•	
fb.com/peterbreuerhamburg		•	
hintergrund.de		•	
blaetter.de		•	
fb.com/dresdenoffenundtolerant		•	
nachdenkseiten.de		•	
faktencheckhellas.org		•	
interventionistische-linke.org		•	
weckerswelt.blog.de		•	
spiegelfechter.com		•	
carta.info		•	
german-foreign-policy.com		•	
weact.campact.de		•	
hotchpotch-blog.de		•	
kraftfuettermischwerk.de		•	
blog.marco-buelow.de		•	
menschenzeitung.de		•	
boeckler.de		•	
zwuckelmann.wordpress.com		•	
oraclesyndicate.twoday.net		•	
syndikalismus.wordpress.com		•	
robert-zion.de		•	
wsws.org		•	
blauerbote.com		•	
dokmz.wordpress.com		•	
fb.com/echte-demokratie-jetzt		•	
fb.com/michel.reimon		•	
project-syndicate.org		•	
globalresearch.ca			•
hinter-den-schlagzeilen.de			•
redglobe.org			•

Social Media Outlets in the Greece Debt Discourse	Left	Center	Right
verfassungsblog.de			.
griechenlandsoliberlin.wordpress.com			.
jef.de			.
netz-gegen-nazis.de			.
berliner-wassertisch.info			.
random-austerity-measure-generator.com			.
fb.com/campact			.
fb.com/griechenlandentscheidet			.
fb.com/snakepage			.
blog.fefe.de			.
goodimpact.org			.
attac.at			.
fb.com/anneclaire.bellier			.
weitwinkelsubjektiv.com			.
ipg-journal.de			.
lostineu.eu			.
zeitschrift-luxemburg.de			.
lawblog.de			.
bildblog.de			.
wirtschaftundgesellschaft.de			.
wurfbude.wordpress.com			.
blog.arbeit-wirtschaft.at			.
aa170.noblogs.org			.
internet-law.de			.
fb.com/mehrdemokratie			.
gjspunk.de			.
omnisophie.com			.
reimon.net			.
sozialismus.info			.
plan-alternative.de			.
amerika21.de			.
fb.com/wolfgang.blau			.
gegenblende.de			.
vineyardsaker.de			.
neuewirtschaftswunder.de			.
attac-netzwerk.de			.
blog.jens-bertrams.de			.
rudifussi.at			.
socialeurope.eu			.
oekonomenstimme.org			.
derblauweisse.wordpress.com			.
egghat.tumblr.com			.
nakedcapitalism.com			.
kraftposts.wordpress.de			.
jazzblog.de			.
kopfzeiler.org			.
maskenfall.de			.
nachrichtenspiegel.de			.
wolfwetzels.wordpress.com			.
business-reframing.de			.
denktagebuch.de			.
fb.com/ichbingrieche			.
fb.com/jungundnaiv			.
abgeordnetenwatch.de			.
mehr-demokratie.de			.
fjhmr.wordpress.com			.
justicenow.de			.
keeptalkinggreece.com			.
deliberationdaily.de			.
gehoertgebloggt.wordpress.com			.
diefreiheitsliebe.de			.
machtelite.wordpress.com			.
bloedermichel.web-xxl.com			.
griechenlandsoli.com			.
fb.com/ultrasagainstra			.
wipokuli.wordpress.com			.
evangelisch.de			.
staatsschuldenuhr.de			.
stopausterity.eu			.
democraticpost.de			.
uweness.eu			.
trueten.de			.
duckhome.net			.
hilfsaktion-gegen-hunger-in-griechenland.de			.
wikileaks.org			.
wienanders.at			.
activism.org			.

Social Media Outlets in the Greece Debt Discourse	Left	Center	Right
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prometheusinstitut.de			•
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